

ATTITUDES OF NIGERIANS TOWARDS MUSHROOMS

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate the attitudes of Nigerians towards the consumption of mushrooms. This study was undertaken at the Southwest area of the country. Two hundred respondents were administered with questionnaires. The technique of analysing was by Likert's scale. In the analysis of data, all responses of strongly agree and agree were grouped under agreement, while strongly disagree and disagree were grouped under disagreement. From the results, the respondents showed positive attitudes towards mushrooms. On this note, we recommended that government and private individuals should embark upon the establishment of mushrooms industries. If these are established and sustained, benefits would include employment generation and others.

KEYWORDS: Mushrooms, mushrooms industry, Likert's scale, positive attitudes, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

Edible mushroom (Fig 1) have for a long time been recognized not only as a delicacy, but also for their use as food in man's diets. Mushrooms have been found to be rich sources of protein, lipids, amino acids, glycogen, vitamins and mineral elements (Aremu *et al.*, 2009). Mushrooms have many uses which range from medicinal, ceremonial, nutritional and biotechnological based functions (Adebayo *et al.*, 2009, Kattawan *et al.*, 2011). Nigeria is a country of many tribes among which are the Hausas in the North, Yorubas in the South West, Urhobo in the Mid – West and the Ibos in the East and each of these tribes has recognized mushrooms for many years using a number of them for various economic and medicinal purposes (Ukoima *et al.*, 2009).

In general, the edible mushrooms have been classified into five categories according to the derivation of their names, namely, those named according to the taste, morphology, growth habit, texture and habitat (Osemwegie *et al.*, 2006). Those classified according to taste are *Volvariella volvacea*, *Volvariella esculenta* which are collectively called Ogiri agbe and *Termitomyces clypeatus*, called Takete. On morphological basis, *Termitomyces mammiformis* is called Rooro while *Termitomyces robustus* is called Ewe. In addition, while *Schizophyllum commune* Fr is called Ese-adie, *Agrocyber broadway* (Murr) is called Gunnugu. Based on growth habit, *Termitomyces globules* and *Pleurotus tuber-reguim* are called Olu whereas on the basis of texture, *Pleurotus squarrosulus* is called Erirokiro and *Psathyrella atroumbonata* is referred to as Wowo. Based on habitat, *Francolimus bicalcaratus* is called Isoaparo because it is believed that this fungus grows and thrives where the droppings of this bird are found. In addition to the above classifications, the natives have observed the growth of many fungi on different kinds of dead wood and have named each fungus after the wood on which it grows (Okhuoya *et al.*, 2010, Abulude and Ndamitso, 2013).

During the oil boom in Nigeria, these edible mushrooms were abandoned for costly alternatives like meat, fish, snail, fish, etc. As the economic situation of the people is dwindling, many had to source for protein alternatives (Abulude, 2012). The question now is what are the attitudes of Nigerians towards mushrooms intake? In the light of this, we have been prompted to address this issue by embanking on this survey. The aim of this paper is therefore to determine the attitudes shown to intake of mushrooms by Nigerians. Suggestions were made on the outcome.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study adopts stratified sampling to capture the various subgroups based on age, sex, and income. The population sampled for this study was the residents of South West Geo-political zone of Nigeria (Lagos, Osun, Ondo, Ogun and Ekiti States). Stratified random sampling technique was used to select 40 respondents (20 males and 20 females) from each of the states, making a total of 200 citizens as the respondents.

Instrumentation

A twenty-item researcher-designed questionnaire was used in this study for the purpose of data collection. The questionnaire was given to experts for construction and content validity of the instrument. The comments and criticism from the experts were used to draft the final version of the questionnaire (Bello, 2014).

Test re-test reliability method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument through the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient and resulted in 0.66, showing that the instrument was reliable.

Questionnaire

Data were collected using a modified enterprise level interview guide that contained open – ended and close – ended questions. The researchers interviewed each respondent interpersonally. Data collected were based on socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, productivity of mushrooms marketing and edible mushrooms species common in the study area, taste, texture, religious belief, preference between meat.

Statistical Analysis

The data gathered were analysed using SPSS Statistics 19 by WebSOFT (frequency, means and percentages).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One hundred percent response rate was recorded. This could be the interest now shown on mushrooms intake. Table 1 shows the results. It was observed that statements 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 had 71, 76, 84, 91 and 87.5%agreements rates. These percentages are positive signals towards mushrooms. The values of 62.5 and 82% recorded for disagreement depicted that not all mushrooms are poisonous and majority believed that religion has nothing to do with mushrooms intake. Less than 20% of the respondents were not sure of what to decide. The 42.5% recorded on cultivation and marketing was expected, the reason been that majority of the respondents were civil servants meaning that there may not be enough time for them to cultivate. Similar effects on quality and acceptability have been reported on soybean products (Yeo, 1984).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In Nigeria, the mushrooms quantities produced or obtained by local farmers are less than intakes of the consumers. It is on this note we are suggesting that stakeholders, government, and researchers should intensify the efforts in cultivating mushrooms on a large scale. Civil servants should be encourage on how to culture so that at their leisure they too can engage on the on the production rather than going to the forest to pick.

REFERENCES

Abulude, F.O (2012). Effect of Different Salts Concentrations on The Functional Properties Of Seven Mushroom Species Obtained In Akure Southwest, Nigeria. Unpublished M. Tech Thesis. Department of Chemistry. Federal University of Technology, Minna.

Abulude, F.O and Ndamitso, M.M (2013): Fungi: A Review on mushrooms. In Current Trends in Advancement of Scientific Research and Opinion in Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology. Edited by Subha Ganguly. Published by Science and Education Development Institute, Nigeria. Chapter 5. Pages 18 – 31. ISBN: 978 – 978 – 52231 – 2 – 5.

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Adebayo, JA, Banjo N. O and Abikoye E. T. (2009). Evaluation of yield oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus pulmonarius*) grown on cotton was and cassava peel. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 8: 215-218.

Aremu MO, Basuk, Gyan S. D, Goyal A, Bhowmik P. K and Datta Banik. S (2009). Proximate composition and functional properties of mushroom flours from *Ganoderma spp*, *Omphalotus Olearius* (DC) sing and *Hebeloma mesphaeum* (Pers) Quels used in Nassarawa State, Nigeria. *Mal of Journal Nutrition*, 15: 233-241.

Bello, Yekeen (2014). Awareness and Knowledge of HIV/AIDS Among Nigerian University Students. *Advances in Agriculture, Sciences and Engineering Research*. 4 (2): 1494 – 1499.

Kattawan A, Chanlekha K, Kongkachuichai R and Chaaroensiri R (2011). Effects of cooking on antioxidant activities and polyphenol content of edible mushrooms commonly consumed in Thailand. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition* 10: 1094-1103.

Okhuoya, J.A.; Akpaja, E.O.; Osemwegie, O.O.; Oghenekaro, A.O.; Ihayaere, C.A. (2010). Nigerian Mushrooms: Underutilized Non-Wood Forest Resources. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 14(1):43-54

Osemwegie OO, E. G. Eriyaremu and J. Abdulmahik (2006). A survey of macrofungi in Edo/Delta region of Nigeria, their morphology and uses. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Science*. 12: 149-157.

Ukoima H.N, Ogbonnaya L.O, Arikpo G. E and Ikpe F. N. (2009) Cultivation of mushroom (*Volvariella volvacea*) on various farm wastes in Obubra Local Government of Cross River State, Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*. 8(7):1052-1054.

Yeo PS (1984). The attitudes of Malaysians towards soybean products. *Patenika*. 7: 95 – 99

Table 1: Results of Attitudes of Consumers on Consumption of Mushrooms

No	Statements	Agree	%	Undecided	%	Disagree	%
1.	I like the taste when cooked	142	71	15	7.5	43	21.5
2.	I like the texture when cooked	152	76	20	10	28	14
3.	Attractive when cooked	168	84	22	11	10	5
4.	I like eating it with different Soups	182	91	10	5	8	4
5.	It is against my religion	15	7.5	21	10.5	164	82
6.	Mushrooms are medicinal	175	87.5	15	7.5	10	5
7.	It is poisonous	25	12.5	20	10	125	62.6
8.	I can cultivate and market	100	50	15	7.5	85	42.5
9.	I prefer it more than meat and fish	110	55	40	20	50	25
10.	Price of mushroom is higher That of meat and fish	10	5	20	10	170	85

Agaricus arvensis

Chloropyllum sp.

Macrolepiota sp.

Pycnoporus cinnabarinus

Tremella fuciformis

Pleurotus porrigens

Pleurotus squarrosolus

Choloma sp

Daldiniacon centrica

Russula sp.

Schizophyllum commune

Scutellinia sp

Thelephora sp

Geastrum saccatus

Microstoma sp.

Unknown

Uricularia auricula.

Fig 1: Some mushroom resources found in Nigeria (Source: Osemwegie (2006))